

The Lamkang Traditional Feasts and Festivals of Manipur: An Identity and History of the Tribe

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Abstract:

Feasts and Festivals play significant features of past and present traditions and society for the Lamkang Tribe of Manipur, North East India. It imparts and preserves their identity and history of the tribe. Celebration and observation of them in the present society may reconnect their root, tradition and culture of the people. This way of practice will signify the identity and history of the people newly. It also inculcates the younger people to conserve, practice and celebrate them in order to relate their identity and history in present society. Discontinuation of past traditions and cultures will be a great lost for the tribe and the onset of vanishing valuable pride, identity and history of the tribe in future. These are the only archives of the tribe to tell the world and people about their identity and history genuinely. Retrospection of the past family and social Feasts and Festivals will restore the unique quality and pride of the tribe's tradition. There are many essential Mores, Ethics and Principles to be learnt from them. This may become a channel of agent to teach and make aware the people from different negative impacts from present world scenario.

Keywords: Feasts and Festivals, Identity, History, Discontinuation, Archives, Retrospection, Essential Mores

Introduction

There is no written documents in the olden Lamkang Society but were only oral traditions, Feasts and Festivals that have passed on to their younger generation to generations about their culture, tradition and all historical facts and events. Their beliefs, observations and celebrations had inculcated the younger people of the society to learn, to continue and to practice through observation and celebration in accordance with the seasons and occasions of the individual, family, village and community throughout a year and generations.

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The socio-traditional Feasts and Festivals play different significant roles in a family life and the societal life of the Lamkang people. These kinds of practices and celebrations of the olden people had unique fundamental principles of the society. Because these are meant to transform, to unite, to reconcile, to inculcate the Mores, to learn etiquette and ethics, to prepare of event, to retrospect lineage and clans, to forgive, to apologize, to celebrate victory, to celebrate child birth, to reconnect its village history, to harvest, to marry, to reminisce, to sow the seed, to appease, to propitiate, to bless, to pray for sick and so on in every aspect of the individual, family and community life. These culture and tradition of the tribe will inculcate the people and the world its rich traditions, identity and history even in this modern society explicitly.

Socio-family feasts and festivals such as *Ngoor-K'shim*, *Saakhu-Juu-Kne/Smul-Knaa*, *Iin-Kluut*, *Miing-Kpuuk*, *Knaa-Kthun*, *Pthlaa-K'kool*, *Pthlaa-kphun/Miindang*, *Kip-Ptiin*, etc build a good relationship among the members and relatives of a family ethically. Socio-community feasts and festivals of the tribe such as *Totlang K'kam*, *Raam-Mun-Ksu*, *Raam-Kvaat*, *Chii-Tlaak*, *Chakhei-Ktun*, *Kumren-Kpartem*, *Dil-K'koor/K'kool*, etc bring a concept of togetherness and oneness in a village and in the tribe generally. In these feasts and festivals, every individual participates, share and celebrate the joy and happiness of the feasts and festivals extravagantly. There is no mine and yours, and no different of status and no discrimination of caste, creed, sex, color, etc. Most of the feasts and festivals of the tribe are related to socio-religious mandatory of the people where a series of religious rituals and sacrifices are performed. For a small tribe like the Lamkang people have only means to tell the world of their origin, identity and history is through continuous celebration of traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe. Otherwise, there is no other documents which can reconnect their past traditions and history in this present society.

In this juncture of the society, the only means to relate their past cultural heritage and identity may be a continuous conservation, observation and celebration of the traditional feasts and festivals by its society without any restraint from among its people and interference of outsiders. It is necessary to mobilize people for introspection and awareness of the past traditional society and the value of their Feasts and Festivals in the present society will ensure a guarantee to codify, to protect and to conserve the tribe's cultural heritage, identity and history in the coming generations. Therefore, only traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe clearly differentiated the peculiarity from the rest of the world of the people, rites, nature, culture and tradition. In this modern world, these may be the only genuine rooted cultural celebration where the ways of practices clearly portray its traditions without other influences. Moreover, these are the rare and original archives of the tribe to tell their identity and history to the present people and society of the world. These will become the most precious tools to introspect the people of their past even in future generation too.

Review of literature

The dearth of knowledge about the Lamkang Tribe of North East India, its culture and people at large by the outsiders and modern writers of the country left unexplored to the modern world. It has different peculiar feasts and festivals that can relate their unique history, tradition and identity of the tribe. The modern historians, scholars and writers could not trace their cultural heritage and historical facts of the tribe in large published books; journals etc. even to this day. This kind of a small piece of work may inform the people and the world in a concise manner about the Lamkang history, culture and their practices and celebrations. Being a small tribe in the North East India, there are no many scholars to delve into the areas and to do research-work about the tribe that also delayed decades to explore their rich past cultural heritage and history until today. This is the main factor why the outsiders, scholars and writers do not know much about the Lamkang tribe, its people, culture and history. Therefore, urgent exploration and extraction of the tribe's feasts and festivals through books, journals etc may impart the contemporary people and world about the Lamkang people's identity and history.

Research Methodology

This research work has employed both descriptive and analytical methods approach to investigate the Feasts and Festivals to explore their identity and historical events of the Lamkang Tribe of Manipur, North East India. Both the primary sources and secondary sources have been used to reconnect the past traditional Feasts and Festivals observation and celebration of the Tribe.

A thorough literature review of was done to build a vital theoretical framework. This involved the analysing of the past Oral tradition, some written documents, interviews, celebration and response of the present people of the tribe

Significance Aspects of Feasts and Festivals

Feasts and Festivals of the Lamkang Tribe of Manipur, North East India have essential principles to inculcate a child, a person, a family and the whole community life through celebration. These observation and celebration occur occasionally in a year in a family and in the community. It is celebrated as mandatory ethical and ritual performance of a family and community of a village or the society. The nature and system of traditional family Feasts and Festivals explicitly impart ethical mores and etiquettes how a children should behave in front of parents and grandparents in a family. Whereas, traditional community Feasts and

Festivals impart selfless-endeavour and sacrifice for the well-being of community as long as he/she lives in the society.

The family feasts and festivals have peculiar features comprise of individual ethics and social mores to be equipped with while observing and celebrating them occasionally. Celebration of such events of family usually enhance a good relationship of the family members that endures lasting love, peace and care in their day-to-day life and generation to generations. For instance, the family feast of 'Ngoor-Kshim' celebration is meant for parents and grandparents to be performed by their children and grandchildren. This celebration of feast will bring conciliation, forgiveness, hospitality, love, caring etc in between parents and children in a family no matter how badly breaches their relationship in the past. While the family feast of 'Smul-Knaa' celebration is meant for married daughter and her children to be performed by her father and her brothers annually. It is celebrated as a symbolic ethical family feast for blessing, caring and love to married daughter and her children through invitation in the beginning of a year. This celebration also inculcates deepen relationship and unavoidable accountability between parents, brothers and their married daughters or sisters. So every family feast and festival has a vital role to play for a family and the society traditionally.

The community feasts and festivals impart the people of selfless service, sacrifice act, and endeavor for the well-being of the community. This also reflects oneness and togetherness whether in difficulty, war, work, joy and happiness in community life. For example, the community feast and festival of 'Totlang-K'kam' portray a generous sharing of wealth to the whole community as a symbol of service, care and love of the society. This act of celebration clearly impart that nobody is individualist in his or her life. The rich people always willing to offer the surplus harvest to society irrespective of their status, wealth, color, sex etc. On the other hand, the community feast and festival of 'Dil-K'koor/K'kool' plays a significant ritual act to be performed by the whole villagers at the end of a year as a symbol to complete their whole year cultivation and harvesting process. In this celebration, the village priest has to perform a series of ritual acts so that to bring home all the souls/spirits of the villagers from jhum places. Otherwise, they believed that some souls/spirits of the villagers might lose in the Jhum places and in forest due to disturbance of malevolent spirits.

To sum up that the traditional Feasts and Festivals of the tribe portray significant aspects in their day-to-day life of the people. The Feasts and Festivals tell the society of time, seasons, occasions, observation, preparation, and so on. These traditions inform the younger people of the tribe theoretically and practically. Every feast and festival educate the young people and children the necessity and ethical obligation in their life to observe and celebrate as long as they live on this earth. This nature of society has been a mechanism

to preserve throughout many generations without written document on it for the people. Therefore, today those traditional Feasts and Festivals of the tribe are the only original archives to be understood as genuine identity and history of the people and the tribe. The Feasts and Festivals reflect all the history, occasions, customs, traditions, journey, origin, people, lifestyle and the like. No other documents can narrate and expound explicitly about the tribe and people than the present traditional Feasts and Festivals observation and celebration.

Objectives of study

The objectives of the study on the Lamkang traditional Feasts and Festivals of Manipur: An Identity and History of the Tribe are as follows:

- To explore the rich traditional Feasts and Festivals of the Tribe for inculcating of their identity and history of the people to the outside world
- To investigate the significance of the Feast and Festivals of the past for conservation and celebration in contemporary Lamkang society
- To distinguish the Lamkang's traditional Feasts and Festivals with the western and other communities Feasts and Festivals
- To identify the value and pride of their traditional Feasts and Festivals in the present society
- To motivate and build a paradigm concept for belongingness and to provide awareness on the gradual vanishing socio-traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe in the people immediately

Limitation

There are numerous hardships and difficulties faced throughout the research work on the Lamkang traditional Feasts and Festivals in shortage of data from both primary and secondary source. Most of the modern scholars and writers do not reach the areas especially on the feasts and festivals of the tribe dare to risk the work undertaken, however, this invigorates the research work more interestingly. Though comprise of several pros and cons in this research work, there is another hope of paradigm shift in this piece of work to change the already influenced concept of the people with mingling of west and neighbouring communities' ideology of cultures and traditions.

It is evident that a small tribe like the Lamkang people of Manipur North East India is not known to the other world about their culture, tradition and history. Thus, many a time misappropriation of the people, culture and language with other groups of people occurred in different writing of the Scholars, writers and

narrators that might be in books, Articles, Newspapers, Journals etc. In addition, their history, culture and land have also been misrepresented in the present society by bigger neighboring communities for meeting of their inhabitant acquisition, expansion of geographical land and political gain in future.

Conclusion

According to this research finding, the coming of modern Christianity, western cultures and other neighbouring cultures has given negative impact on their own socio-traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe. The contemporary Lamkang society has faced gradual assimilation of modernization and westernization. The present Lamkang people have a dilemma concept to whether degrade their own tradition to embrace other new culture and tradition for betterment and convenient of the people.

The continuous celebration of traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe will ignite the mind and concept of the people to start valuing their own tradition. No matter how far gone or left the feasts and festivals of the tribe by the people, there is still a ray of hope to reinstate the vibrant and significant tradition of the past in this present society. The retrospection and introspection among the contemporary Lamkang people will enhance to revive their past tradition and heritage through proper mobilization and awareness on the matter. The most valuable features in any tribe or society is the way how people pass on the traditions, celebrate the feasts and festivals and reconnect their identity and history through observation, celebration and conservation in the younger generations.

Traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe have a valid significance to retell their origin, people, way of life and celebration, identity of the tribe and immemorial history through them. Oral history has slowly misinformed the younger people due to social ignorance on the system, a rapid change of modern world of society with advancement of science and technology and present digital society. In this situation of the world of society, it is required to revive their past culture especially the traditional feasts and festivals of the tribe so that they can impart their history, identity and culture to the younger generations through observation and celebration in their day-to-day life of the society.

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